

**THE METHODS OF RENDERING IMPLACATURE IN SIMULTANEOUS
INTERPRETATION OF PUBLIC SPEECHES**

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Annotation

In this article one of the types of simultaneous interpreting is considered. We determine characteristics that distinguish it from other interpreting types. Also we determine events, where simultaneous interpreting is applicable. Besides that, one can find out a few interesting facts about it. In the article we consider advantages and disadvantages of simultaneous interpreting

Keywords: simultaneous interpreting, types, advantages and disadvantages of simultaneous interpreting, Speshnev

Аннотация

В данной статье подробно рассмотрен один из видов переводов – синхронный перевод. Определены характеристики, отличающие его от иных видов перевода, а также мероприятия, на которых он применяется. Кроме того, в данной статье вы сможете узнать несколько интересных фактов о нем. В статье проанализированы положительные и отрицательные стороны синхронного перевода

Ключевые слова: синхронный перевод, виды, достоинства и недостатки синхронного перевода, Спешнев

The modes of interpreting have evolved through time. Three modes are now recognized by the interpreting profession and have been adopted in federal and state statutes and court rules: simultaneous interpreting, consecutive interpreting, and sight translation. Each mode fits particular needs. We will try to explain the use of simultaneous interpreting and provide practical suggestions for effective use of

interpreters when working with individuals with limited English proficiency (LEP) [1].

What is simultaneous interpreting?

Simultaneous interpreting is the rendering of one spoken language into another when running renditions are needed at the same time as the English language communication. The interpreter speaks virtually at the same time as the LEP person. When done properly, it is a true and accurate interpretation of one language to another, done without omissions or embellishments, so that the parties can understand one another quickly. Types of simultaneous interpreting Simultaneous interpreting is delivered as the speaker talks, but the interpretation may be given in different ways.

Today there are three basic types of interpreting used at business meetings, conferences and workshops:

- “By listening” is the most popular. In this case the interpreter wears headphones to listen to the speaker and renders the speech in blocks.
- “At sight” ranks second by demand. The specialist is provided with a text of the speech in writing beforehand and interprets from that source. If the speaker deviates from the text the interpreter adjusts it accordingly.
- Simultaneous reading of a pre-translated text is the least common. A simultaneous interpreter reads a pre-translated text and adjusts the interpretation if the speaker gives examples, makes corrections or answers questions [2].

Advantages of simultaneous interpreting

Comparison between consecutive and simultaneous interpreting reveals that the latter has two major advantages, at least for use at large events. Firstly, it halves the length of a meeting, conference or negotiations. Participants do not have to wait for the speaker to finish speaking to listen to the interpretation. They are simultaneously provided with the speech in their native language. Secondly, simultaneous interpreting helps the speaker to feel the audience’s mood and respond to their reaction in real time. This is vitally important at training events, seminars

and public appearances when the success of the event and the “energy” of the audience largely depend on the speaker.

Disadvantages of simultaneous interpreting for both sides might be firstly, simultaneous interpreting would be more inaccurate translation comparing with other types of translation. Secondly, the process is stressful. Payment also might be highlighted as disadvantage [3].

When to Use Simultaneous Interpreting

In simultaneous interpreting, also known as conference interpreting, the interpretation is transmitted to listeners in real time while the original speech is still in progress. Simultaneous interpreting is primarily used in formal or large group settings, where one person is speaking in front of an audience, rather than in conversational environments. These events can include:

- Diplomatic conferences
- International conventions
- Business or board meetings
- Training sessions o Courtrooms
- Lectures and presentations
- Tours [4]

This type of interpreting frequently requires audiovisual equipment, such as wireless receivers, headsets and microphones, to relay messages quickly to a large audience. How to prepare for simultaneous interpreting Each simultaneous interpreter needs to know how to prepare properly. A translation agency will certainly take care of most of the organization.

However, if interpreter wants the very best quality, his input will be needed as well:

1. Identify the languages into which interpreting will be delivered. Each participant should receive information in his or her mother tongue; if any guests miss out on this, they may feel forgotten and have a poor impression of the standard of organization at the event.

2. Provide the simultaneous interpreters with materials on the topic to be discussed. An interpreter should learn beforehand the subject and terminology of an event.

3. Prepare the premises for event, providing interpreting booths, headphones and microphones, and, in some cases, loudspeakers, amplifiers and projectors.

4. Make an order for interpreting well in advance, so that the interpreters can prepare for event. Simultaneous interpreter profession is very rare and complicated. Russia is famous for its simultaneous interpreters.

One of the most famous and successful Russian interpreters was N.A. Speshnev [5]. He was master of his craft but the most prominent period of work was time when he worked as Gorbachov's interpreter. Speshnev took a great part in dealing with China. In 1989 year Gorbachov met with Den Syaopin after that relations between Russia and China started to normalize [6].

To conclude with interesting facts about simultaneous interpreting:

- The simultaneous interpreting equipment in the hall of the Kremlin Palace of Congresses makes it possible to provide interpreting into 29 languages at the same time. At the United Nations in interpretation is carried out in only five or six languages at the same time.

- The most requested language combinations are interpreting from Russian into English, German and French

- A patent for simultaneous company in favour of the radio engineer Finley Gordon in 1926, but the first use of simultaneous interpreting anywhere in the world, was in 1928, in the USSR, during the sixth Communist International Congress.

- It is believed that simultaneous interpreting became widespread after its use at the Nuremberg trials of Nazi war criminals.

- The simultaneous interpreting equipment in the hall of the Kremlin Palace of Congresses makes it possible to provide interpreting into 29 languages New York and Geneva simultaneous interpretation is carried out in only five or six languages at the same time.

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